

The Dark Side of Signals: Patents Protecting Radical Inventions and Venture Capital Investments

[Running head: The Dark Side of Signals]

Massimo G. Colombo
Department of Management, Economics, and Industrial Engineering
Politecnico di Milano
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci, 32
20133 Milan, Italy
Phone: +39 02 2399-2748
Email: massimo.colombo@polimi.it

Massimiliano Guerini
Department of Management, Economics, and Industrial Engineering
Politecnico di Milano
Piazza Leonardo da Vinci, 32
20133 Milan, Italy
Phone: +39 02 2399-2748
Email: massimiliano.guerini@polimi.it

Karin Hoisl*
Mannheim Business School
University of Mannheim
L5, 4
68161 Mannheim, Germany
Phone: +49 (0)621 181-1604
Email: hoisl@bwl.uni-mannheim.de

Nico Zeiner
Mannheim Business School
University of Mannheim
L5, 4
68161 Mannheim, Germany
Phone: +49 (0)621 181-1604
Email: nico.zeiner@uni-mannheim.de

* Corresponding author

Keywords: signal, venture capital, radical invention, reputable investor, syndication

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates signals that convey positive and negative information at the same time, i.e., that have a dark side. We analyze 362 young European life science companies that received first-round investments from 281 venture capital (VC) investors between 2003 and 2015. We study how VC investors react to patents protecting radical inventions, which offer tremendous profit opportunities but have a high risk of failure (dark side). We show that these companies are attractive investment targets for reputable VC investors but not for nonreputable ones and that these reputable investors take action by syndicating their investments. Hence, the dark side of the signal leads to both a reevaluation of the information content of the signal and an action to reduce the tension.

Acknowledgements:

This work was supported by RISIS2 (Research Infrastructure for and Innovation Policy Studies 2), funded by the European Union's Horizon2020 Research and innovation programme under the grant number n°824091.

The Dark Side of Signals: Patents Protecting Radical Inventions and Venture Capital Investments

INTRODUCTION

Signals have long been investigated in the economics and management literature (Spence, 1973; 2002). They are of interest since they facilitate transactions under information asymmetry (Stiglitz, 2000; 2002). Signals are credible if they are costly to obtain and correlated with quality so that only high-quality actors have an incentive to invest in the signal. Under these conditions, signals result in a separating equilibrium, allowing uninformed third parties to disentangle high-quality actors from low-quality ones (for reviews see Connelly et al., 2011; Bergh et al., 2014). Signals conveying quality information inherently have a positive connotation (Spence, 2002; Stiglitz, 2002). However, they can also have a negative side, i.e., carry negative information in addition to positive information. This “dark side of signals” has, so far, escaped systematic analysis. The dark side is important, since conflicting information leads to imbalance and psychological tension, i.e., stress (Heider, 1958). Research has shown that whereas small amounts of stress increase motivation and arousal and consequently performance, an excessively high degree of stress leads to anxiety and impairs performance (Anderson, 1976). This negative relationship between tension and performance leads us to investigate how to deal with the dark side of signals.

Based on signaling theory and balance theory, we argue that the dark side of a signal leads to psychological tension. To move from tension to a balanced state, actors have two options: (1) actions to reduce or eliminate tension or (2) cognitive reorganization, i.e., a reevaluation of the situation (Opp, 1984). Our paper aims to answer the question of how receivers of signals react in case the signal also has a dark side.

This paper contributes to the signaling literature by analyzing signals that convey good and bad information at the same time. The existing literature has dealt with multiple signals, which may overburden a receiver characterized by bounded rationality (Pollock et al., 2010, Stern et al., 2014). The paper by Drover et al. (2018) is one of the few works that analyzes multiple conflicting signals. However, whereas multiple signals allow for conscious or subconscious selective cognition, i.e., a focus on selected signals while the others are ignored, psychological tension cannot be avoided in cases in which conflicting information is contained in a single signal.

A second contribution is our research design, which enables a test of how receivers react to the dark side of a signal. We choose the context of venture capital (VC) financing of young companies. Some of the companies we observe own patents protecting radical inventions, i.e., those combining knowledge components that had previously not been combined (Schumpeter, 1934; Fleming, 2001; Dahlin and Behrens, 2005). Patents can be considered a signal since they are expensive and only granted for inventions that are new, involve an inventive step and are commercially applicable. Furthermore, entrepreneurship scholars have shown that patents can help young companies secure the required resources, since patents are observable attributes that are related to the unknown quality of young companies. Patents thus reduce the information asymmetry between founders and investors and, thereby, the (perceived) investment risk (Stuart et al., 1999; Hsu and Ziedonis, 2008).

Patents protecting radical inventions convey a signal of tremendous earning potential (Trajtenberg, 1990; Ahuja and Lampert, 2001). However, they also require high investment sums for this potential to be realized and are characterized by a high risk of failure and delayed returns (Atuahene-Gima, 2005; Rubera and Kirca, 2012; Nanda and Rhodes-Kropf, 2013). Hence, there is a dark side of the signal, as well.

Balance theory predicts that VC investors follow one or both modes to cope with the imbalance and psychological tension resulting from conflicting information: take action and/or engage in cognitive reorganization. One possible action to deal with the dark side of the signal is syndication, i.e., the inclusion of two or more investors in the same investment round (Bygrave, 1987; Lerner, 1994). Syndication allows for risk sharing among partners (Wright and Lockett, 2003). Additionally, syndication partners provide a second opinion, which may lead to better informed decision making (Lerner, 1994; Brander et al., 2002). The pooled resources of all syndicated partners also facilitate providing young companies with the resources required to successfully exploit their business ideas (Brander et al., 2002; Dimov and Milanov, 2010; Bayar et al., 2019). Cognitive reorganization could mean that radical inventions are interpreted differently depending on the characteristics of the investors. Highly reputable investors may be less discouraged by the dark side of a signal than less reputable investors (Petkova et al., 2014). This is because the reputational damage in case of failure should be less pronounced for reputable investors (Pfarrer et al., 2010).

We use a subsample of the VICO (RISIS EC-H2020) data. These data provide geographical, industry, and accounting information on companies in 28 European countries and Israel that received at least one VC investment between January 2003 and March 2015 when they were 10 years old or younger. The young companies in our sample all filed at least one patent application with the European Patent Office (EPO) or the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). The companies represent a positive selection in terms of quality. This makes sure that extreme quality differentials among young companies do not bias our results.

We focus our analysis on companies active in the life sciences (most of the companies in our sample are active in biotechnology (45 percent), medical instruments (26 percent), or pharmaceuticals (15 percent)), since this branch of science is characterized by a high patent propensity, high capital requirements, and vivid startup activity (Cohen and Walsh, 2002;

Nasto, 2008). Information on patent filings extracted from the PATSTAT database of the EPO. PATSTAT contains bibliographic patent data from more than 100 patent offices worldwide. Investment histories of the identified investors covering 1980 to 2015 were extracted from the Thomson Reuters EIKON PE database, which contains over 30 years' worth of historical information, updated daily, on private equity and VC firms, funds, and investee companies worldwide. Our final sample consists of 281 VC investors and 362 companies. Nineteen percent of these companies filed at least one patent application with the EPO or WIPO for a radical invention before the date of receiving their first VC investment.

To test our hypotheses, we use a matching model. More precisely, we model the probability that a focal company has an investment tie with a focal VC investor and that this tie corresponds to either a standalone or a syndicated investment. We investigate how these probabilities vary depending on the characteristics of the companies (i.e., whether they have developed one or more radical inventions) and of the VC investors (their reputation). To do so, we assess the 436 realized company-VC investor ties against a counterfactual of unrealized company-VC investor ties that could have formed. A multinomial logit comparing the alternative outcomes “unrealized tie”, “standalone tie” and “syndicated tie” provides evidence that VC investors indeed use the two coping mechanisms to reach cognitive consistency and, consequently, psychological balance. In particular, we find that when a company has at least one radical invention compared to no radical inventions, the probability of a syndicated deal increases by 40 percent. We also find that more reputable VC investors are more attracted than other VC investors to companies having developed radical inventions. Again, reputable investors prefer to syndicate rather than invest alone in this scenario. The probability of a syndicated tie with a highly reputable VC investor increases by 140 percent when a company has at least one radical invention. In sum, our results are both statistically and economically significant.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Signaling theory

Signaling theory is concerned with reducing the negative effects of information asymmetry and helps explain decisions in transactions where one party has more information than the other (Spence, 1973; 2002; Stiglitz, 2002). Information asymmetry occurs when part of the information required for decision-making is private instead of public. Information that is normally private is information about quality and intent (Stiglitz, 2000). The former refers to a situation where one party cannot perfectly observe or assess the quality of a transaction partner or that of the product or service that is part of the transaction. The latter characterizes a situation where the behavior or the underlying intentions of the transaction partner cannot be observed or understood (Elitzur and Gaviious, 2003).

One way to overcome information asymmetry is to rely on *signals*. Signals are observable actions that are positively correlated with quality and convey information about intentions (Spence, 1973; 2002). Signals are effective, i.e., credible, when they are costly to obtain and when the costs are lower for high-quality firms or individuals, making signaling a positive return strategy only for these firms and individuals. Under these circumstances, sending a signal leads to a separating equilibrium, revealing the true unobserved quality of firms or individuals (Bergh et al., 2014). Hsu and Ziedonis (2008), for instance, investigate the signaling value of patents for high-tech startups and the conditions under which this value is particularly effective or limited. The results show that patents qualify as signals that are most effective in the early development stages, when uncertainty and financial needs are high.

The dark side of signals

Whereas signaling theory and the conceptual and empirical work that builds on this theory interpret a signal as inherently positive, there might also be negative information attached to a signal; i.e., signals may have a dark side.

The signaling literature recognizes that signals do not always convey valuable information. Works dealing with multiple signals show that signals have positive additive effects when they convey information relating to complementary domains (e.g., the status and reputation of entrepreneurs (Stern et al., 2014) and the science domain and the business and finance domains (Colombo et al., 2019b)). Overlapping signals pertaining to two similar domains (such as IPO firms' affiliation with several prestigious VC investors and underwriters (Pollock et al., 2010)), conversely, are redundant and have limited additional information value.

More recently, scholars have argued that individuals frequently need to interpret bundles of signals that may convey incongruent information (Connelly et al., 2011) and have addressed how individuals characterized by bounded rationality (Simon, 1991) process these complex bundles of signals. Drover et al. (2018), for instance, develop a theory of how boundedly rational individuals deal with the cognitively difficult task of attending to and interpreting a large number of contradictory (i.e., positive and negative) signals.¹ The authors suggest that individuals initially attend to a different number of signals depending on the type of cognitive processes in use (top-down, goal-driven, systematic cognitive processes vs. bottom-up, stimulus-driven, heuristic cognitive processes). In a second step, the individuals resort to one or the other type of cognitive process to interpret a given bundle of signals based on its combined valence, i.e., the number and strength of the positive and negative signals composing the bundle.

Even though this literature has advanced our understanding of the complex task of processing multiple signals, it does not address situations where the conflict is created by conflicting, i.e.,

¹ Spence (1973) makes an important distinction between observable inalterable attributes of an individual (or firm) like gender and race and alterable attributes that the individual (or firm) can manipulate by bearing some costs. He reserves the term "signal" for these manipulable and costly attributes, while he calls the inalterable attributes "indices". As a corollary, while indices may convey fully negative information, signals cannot, as individuals (and firms) have no incentive to bear a cost to communicate negative information. In the subsequent signaling literature, the distinction between signals and indices has often been lost. Indeed, scholars have considered "rhetoric signals" (Steigenberger and Wilhelm, 2018), the cost of which is independent of the quality of the sender, and "negative signals" (Drover et al., 2018), which convey fully negative information.

positive and negative information sent by *a single signal*. Individuals who are confronted with multiple signals and who cannot realize a satisfactory level of judgmental confidence preferably resort to faster heuristic cognitive processes and proceed to a systematic evaluation of the information content of the different signals (Drover et al., 2018). Accordingly, when there are multiple conflicting signals, individuals typically focus on more observable, stronger signals that are coherent with each other and discard the remaining signals (i.e., discard the negative signals when most signals are positive or vice versa, a situation called “imbalanced incongruence”). However, in the case of balanced incongruence, when there are both positive and negative signals, individuals are forced to systematically evaluate the different signals and may even suspend their judgment if positive and negative signals are both strong enough.

In case a decision is based on a single signal that conveys conflicting information, i.e., a signal with a dark side, it is harder for individuals to ignore the negative information that is sent by the signal. In fact, ignoring this negative information leads to a conflict, since part of the signal would have to be considered important whereas another part of it would have to be considered not important.

Balance theory, originally proposed by Fritz Heider (1958), can help to understand the cognitive processes that may be triggered by signals sending combined conflicting information. The theory assumes that individuals strive for cognitive consistency to reach psychological balance. The units of analysis of Heider’s theory are sociocognitive networks consisting of three nodes (e.g., three individuals, A, B, and C) that are linked to each other. Imbalance refers to a network where, for instance, A likes B but dislikes C and thinks that B likes C (Adejumo et al., 2008). Transferred to a situation of a signal conveying conflicting information, this dynamic would mean that the decision maker likes the positive but not the negative information conveyed by a signal and needs to consider both pieces of information in some way to make a decision. The fact that the liked and disliked information comes from a unique information source leads to

imbalance and consequently to inconsistency and psychological tension. To eliminate or at least decrease tension, i.e., to move from an imbalanced towards a (more) balanced state, individuals have two options: (1) action or (2) cognitive reorganization (Opp, 1984).

In the case of conflicting information sent by one signal, action involves trying to influence the outcome to alleviate the effects of the negative information conveyed by the signal. Cognitive reorganization involves restructuring the cognitive representation of the situation generated by the incongruent information conveyed by the signal, enabling a solution—i.e., differently categorizing the positive and negative information or changing the attitude towards the outcome (e.g., through reevaluation) (Adejumo et al., 2008). A change in attitude towards the outcome relates to the perception of the signal. Signaling typically requires two parties, the sender (i.e., the signaler) and the receiver (Connelly et al., 2011). In a simplified model, we can assume a dyad, i.e., one sender and one receiver, though the concepts would also apply to multiple senders and receivers. The sender encodes and sends the quality signal, and the receiver decodes and interprets the signal against the background of her own experience and characteristics (Shannon and Weaver, 1949). If the experience or the characteristics of the receiver allow for interpreting the dark side of a signal in a way that the dark side is less “threatening”, this could lead to the reevaluation of the signal to give more emphasis to the positive information it conveys (Vanacker and Forbes, 2016).

THE DARK SIDE OF SIGNALS AND THE FINANCING OF YOUNG COMPANIES

The search of a young innovative company for external equity is characterized by information asymmetry (Carpenter and Petersen, 2002; Hall and Lerner, 2010). For external investors, it is difficult to assess the quality of a young innovative company, since these firms do not have a track record, are not yet profitable, and most of their assets are intangible (Denis, 2004). At least part of the information about the quality of the firms is private, i.e., known to the entrepreneurs but not to outside investors. Entrepreneurs are reluctant to divulge these details

to third parties because of concerns about possible information leakages and misuse (Dushnitsky and Shaver, 2009; Colombo and Shafi, 2016). Moreover, entrepreneurs may exploit their information advantage and overstate the quality of their venture to increase the likelihood of acquiring funding or to reach better deals² (Shane and Stuart, 2002).

Unobservable quality refers to the quality of both the entrepreneurs and the technology their companies have developed. For entrepreneurs, educational attainment and work experience, including experience as an entrepreneur, may be an effective signal (Deeds et al., 2004; Higgins and Gulati, 2006; Hsu, 2007; Hoenig and Henkel, 2015). For the technology, patents qualify as a signal (Hsu and Ziedonis, 2008; Hoenen et al., 2014; Deeds et al., 1997). Filing a patent is costly, and examiners at patent offices issue an objective certificate of the quality of an invention if the invention fulfills the requirements of patentability: novelty, an inventive step, and commercial applicability.

We assume that patents protecting radical inventions, defined as those combining knowledge components that have previously not been combined (Schumpeter, 1934; Fleming, 2001; Dahlin and Behrens, 2005), are an example of a signal with a dark side, i.e., a signal that conveys both positive and negative information. Radical inventions have tremendous earning potential (Ahuja and Lampert, 2001; Trajtenberg, 1990) and are considered instrumental for the long-term success of firms (Dewar and Dutton, 1986; McDermott and O'Connor, 2002; Raisch and Birkinshaw, 2008; Rubera and Kirca, 2012). However, such inventions also require high investment sums and are characterized by a high risk of failure and delayed returns (Nanda and Rhodes-Kropf, 2013). The positive and dark sides of the signal lead to imbalance and psychological tension on the part of possible investors.

² Principal-agent theory argues that there is information asymmetry regarding the intentions of the entrepreneurs, as well, which could lead to moral hazard. If entrepreneurs obtain funding, they might have an incentive to misallocate financial resources or decrease the effort put into building the young firm (Kaplan and Strömberg, 2004; Nofsinger and Wang, 2011).

To reach a balanced state, investors can take action. This would typically mean that they syndicate. Forming a syndicate means that two or more investors join forces and invest in a company in the same investment round (Bygrave, 1987). Syndication allows investors to pool their financial resources and to share the risks of investments (Wright and Lockett, 2003). These risks are clearly higher for investments in young companies with radical inventions, making syndication more appealing. Syndication entails two additional advantages that are especially important for investments in this type of companies. In the pre-financing stage, syndication partners provide a second opinion on deals, which typically leads to better informed decision making (Brander et al., 2002; Lerner, 1994). For investors, it is extremely difficult to assess the returns on their investments in companies that have developed radical inventions, which increases the value of having an informed second opinion. In the post-financing stage, syndication partners can pool their (allegedly complementary) resources and experience to optimally support investee companies (Brander et al., 2002; Bayar et al., 2019). Being backed by a pool of investors with heterogeneous resources and experiences again is more beneficial for young companies that have developed radical inventions, as it is difficult to determine in advance which type of asset is needed for the commercial exploitation of these inventions.

Previous empirical studies on VC syndicates indirectly support our contention that investments in young companies with radical inventions are more likely to be syndicated. These studies show that VC investors tend to syndicate when they enter industries where they lack the required experience to make a well-informed decision or to nurture a young company (Dimov and Milanov, 2010). They are also more likely to syndicate when investing in companies with more complex and riskier projects (Bayar et al., 2019). Hypothesis 1 follows.

Hypothesis 1: An investment in a young innovative company is more likely to be syndicated if the company has a radical invention.

The second possibility to achieve a balanced state is cognitive reorganization, i.e., reevaluation. Different types of investors (receivers) may interpret the dark side of a signal sent by radical inventions differently. In this context, the reputation of the VC investor seems to be important (Lee et al., 2011). Reputation is defined as stakeholders' perception of a firm's ability to deliver value based on its past action (Fombrun, 1996; Rindova and Fombrun, 1999). Highly reputable VC investors are less likely to be discouraged by the dark side of a signal than their less reputable competitors; i.e., they are more likely to consider investing in companies with a higher risk of failure (Petkova et al., 2014). We mentioned above that failure has two consequences: financial loss and reputational damage. While the financial loss is the same for all types of investors, this does not apply to damage to reputation. Highly reputable VC investors exhibit a consistent track record of previous successful investments and, hence, can be expected to experience greater rewards from stakeholders for positive outcomes and smaller penalties for negative outcomes than those experienced by less reputable (and less successful) VC investors (Pfarrer et al., 2010). In the case of reputable VC investors, positive outcomes are likely to be attributed to the capabilities of the investors, whereas negative outcomes are attributed to bad luck. Conversely, for non-reputable VC investors, negative outcomes can be detrimental, since the stigma of failure may undermine their attempt to build a reputation.

Second, reputable VC investors are typically more experienced. This is because they have been in business for a long time and are attractive partners for entrepreneurs, which leads to more deals (Pollock et al., 2004). More experienced VC investors can be assumed to know better how to assess and deal with the risk involved in radical inventions than less experienced investors.

Last, reputation increases a firm's confidence in its own abilities (Fombrun, 1996). Highly reputable VC investors, being more confident, may set higher aspiration levels than other VC investors (Petkova et al., 2014). This may cause them to reevaluate the incongruent information

associated with the signal conveyed by radical inventions. In particular, this may lead to a discarding of the dark side of the signal. Consequently, companies that have developed radical inventions may be considered to present promising new investment opportunities.³ These arguments lead to hypothesis 2.

Hypothesis 2: An investment in a young innovative company is more likely to be made by a reputable investor if the company has a radical invention.

DATA AND METHOD

Data source and sample

To test our hypotheses, we focus on young VC-backed companies that are active in the life sciences. This is an ideal testbed for our study. In this science-oriented industry, commercial applications have a direct link with basic research, and radical inventions are potentially a fundamental source of competitive advantage for young companies (de Vet and Scott, 1992; Zucker et al., 1998; Azoulay et al., 2011; Kolympiris et al., 2014). However, for VC investors, assessing the market potential of companies' inventions, especially the more radical ones, is a difficult task because of the long lag between the development of inventions and their commercial applications (Junkunc, 2007; Honeysett and Metheny, 2012). In addition, life science companies are reluctant to diffuse information about their inventions because of the risk of misappropriation of the associated knowledge (Deeds et al., 1997; Janney and Folta, 2003). Hence, radical inventions make companies an attractive but very risky target for VC investment. We consider patent information to characterize the radicalness of each company's portfolio of inventions at the time of receipt of the first VC investment and information on the characteristics of VC investors over time to determine their level of reputation.

³ One reputable VC investor, cited by Petkova et al. (2014, p. 425), states, "We typically try not to invest in anything that's just going to move the needle a little bit, but that is going to be a completely revolutionary."

To this end, we combine several data sources. First, we use the VICO (edition 4.0) dataset to identify companies in life sciences that received at least one round of VC. The dataset was created as part of the RISIS research project, funded by the European Commission, and it contains information on VC investment deals completed in the period 1998-2015 in companies located in EU-27 countries, the UK and Israel and reported in the commercial databases Zephyr, Crunchbase and Thomson ONE.⁴ It includes information on VC-backed companies (e.g., name, location, industry of operation, founding date), VC investors (e.g., investor name, investor governance, location, age), and investment deals (e.g., investment date, investment round). To identify companies that were active in the life sciences, we use Eurostat NACE Rev. 2 industry classification codes⁵. Based on the industry information, we are able to identify 1,424 VC-backed life science companies. We then exclude companies that were older than 10 years when receiving the first round of VC (as we are interested in young companies) and restrict our investment period to the years 2003-2015, as we need a 5-year window before the date of a focal investment to construct our measures of the investor's reputation. Applying these two criteria leads to a sample of 875 young life science companies. Last, we exclude companies financed by captive VC investors (e.g., corporate or governmental VC). The investment behavior of captive VC investors is also driven by nonfinancial objectives and differs substantially from that of independent VC investors (Bertoni et al., 2015; 2019a). We finally identify 703 life science companies that were 10 years old or younger at the date of the receipt of the first VC investment round and that received first-round investments from 670 distinct independent VC investors between 2003 and 2015.

⁴ The RISIS project resulted in a dataset containing 68,698 VC investment deals made by 8,761 investors in 24,238 companies. See <http://risis.eu> (accessed on September 20, 2019) for more details.

⁵ Companies classified under the following codes were added to our sample: 21 (*Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations*), 26.6 (*Manufacture of irradiation, electro-medical and electrotherapeutic equipment*), 32.5 (*Manufacture of medical and dental instruments and supplies*), 46.46 (*Wholesale of pharmaceutical goods*), 47.73 (*Dispensing chemist in specialized stores*), 47.74 (*Retail sale of medical and orthopedic goods in specialized stores*), 72.11 (*Research and experimental development on biotechnology*), 86 (*Human health activities*), 87 (*Residential care activities*), 96.04 (*Physical well-being activities*), and 96.09 (*Other personal service activities n.e.c.*).

Second, we collect patent information on the identified companies. Patents are extracted from PATSTAT (2018 Spring Edition)⁶, a patent database containing bibliographical and legal status patent data from leading industrialized and developing countries. We trace the patent histories of the identified companies by matching the company names reported in VICO with the applicant names listed in PATSTAT. Since the companies in our sample are located in Europe and since patent filings from national patent offices cannot be straightforwardly compared due to country-specific examination or grant procedures⁷, we only extract patent applications filed with the EPO and WIPO.

We start from the population of patents filed with the EPO and WIPO between 1978 and 2015. Before performing the matching, we clean the company names in VICO by removing legal status suffixes (e.g., AG, GmbH, SpA), generic terms (e.g., international, Europe, Germany), and special characters. The name matching is conducted using a string match, i.e., by directly comparing the names of the companies with the applicant names. The string match is checked manually to ensure the accuracy of name matching. Furthermore, we cross-check the matching results with manual patent searches using the online version of the European Patent Register⁸. From the previously identified 703 life science companies, 509 filed at least one patent. For these companies, we identify 5,203 patent applications (EPO: 77 percent; WIPO: 23 percent) between 1988 and 2015 that were either granted or still pending at the time of the first VC investment round. We exclude withdrawn, refused, or revoked patent applications. As a robustness check, we also exclude pending patents before calculating our radicalness measures, since one could argue that pending patents do not send a (strong) signal. Our results remain robust with respect to the sign and the size of the coefficients as well as significance.⁹

⁶ See <https://www.epo.org/searching-for-patents/business/patstat.html#tab-1> (accessed on September 20, 2019).

⁷ For instance, some countries allow deferred patent examination, while others do not (Harhoff, 2016).

⁸ See <https://register.epo.org> (accessed on September 20, 2019).

⁹ The results of this robustness check are available from the authors upon request.

The identified patent applications belong to 3,652 patent families, i.e., groups of patent documents protecting the same invention in different jurisdictions. Since one patent family can contain more than one patent protecting the same invention, we conduct our analysis at the level of the patent family. We add bibliographic and procedural information on the respective patents. This information allows us to identify radical inventions and to control for the quality of the patents. Since we are interested in the signals patents convey to VC investors, we select only those companies with at least one patent filed before the company received its first round of VC, i.e., 385 companies with 1,591 inventions (patent families).

Third, to build our reputation measures, we need information about earlier investments of the independent VC investors who invested in these companies. The VICO dataset only contains information VC investments in Europe. Hence, we collect information on investments made by VC investors outside of Europe using the Thomson Reuters Eikon Private Equity database. We add information on the number of VC investments (worldwide) between 1980 and 2015 made by the focal VC investor, its industry focus¹⁰, and performance (i.e., successful exit through IPO). After we drop companies and VC investors with missing data, our final sample contains 362 young European life science companies that received their first round of VC from 281 independent VC investors during the period 2003-2015. Since parts of the investments were syndicated investments, our dataset contains 436 realized investment ties (standalone ties: 23.6 percent; syndicated ties: 76.4 percent). Overall, the 362 companies in our sample have 1,516 patent families before receiving a first round of VC financing.

Description of the variables

Dependent variable

¹⁰ We convert the NAICS classifications from Eikon into NACE classifications (4-digit) using a concordance table from Eurostat to be consistent in the identification of life science companies (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/ramon/index.cfm?TargetUrl=DSP_PUB_WELC_, accessed on September 19, 2019).

We use a matching model where the dependent variable *Dealtype* is a categorical variable that equals 0 for unrealized investment ties, 1 for standalone realized investment ties, and 2 for syndicated realized investment ties between company *i* and VC investor *j*.

Independent variables

Radical Invention. The variable *Radical Invention* is a dummy variable that equals 1 for companies with at least one radical invention before the receipt of a first round of VC financing. To identify radical inventions, we follow the approach of Verhoeven et al. (2016), who build on seminal work from Fleming et al. (2007). Verhoeven et al. (2016) define an invention as novel in recombination (i.e., radical), if the combination of its components and principles applied are different from those embodied in all previous inventions. We use the International Patent Classification (IPC) codes¹¹ assigned to an invention for which patent protection was sought as a proxy for the knowledge components underlying an invention. An invention is considered radical if the invention (i.e., all documents of a DOCDB patent family) contains at least one pair of IPC classes that had previously not been combined.

We rely on the PATSTAT Spring 2018 version and use all 16,466,638 patent applications¹² (10,494,906 DOCDB patent families) filed with the EPO, the US Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO), and the WIPO between 1980 and 2015 to identify radical inventions. In a first step, we create all unique IPC class pairs (main group level—seven-digit) for the DOCDB patent families containing at least one patent filed with the EPO, USPTO and WIPO. In a second step, we identify the first occurrence of a specific IPC class pair and define the associated invention (i.e., the DOCDB patent family) as radical. Based on this information, we identify the

¹¹ The IPC classification provides for a hierarchical system to codify patents according to the different areas of technology to which they pertain. It hierarchically uses 8 sections, 131 classes, 645 subclasses, 7,483 main groups and 67,020 subgroups as of January 2019. See <https://www.wipo.int/classifications/ipc/en/> (accessed on September 19, 2019) for details.

¹² The PATSTAT Spring 2018 version consists of 84,375,547 applications with a subsequent publication. See <https://www.epo.org/searching-for-patents/business/patstat.html/> (accessed on November 21, 2019) for details. Thus, the patent applications we use as a basis for the identification of radical inventions cover 19.5 percent of all patent filings worldwide.

companies in our sample that filed a patent for at least one radical invention before obtaining their first round of funding by a VC (*Radical Invention* = 1). Out of the 1,516 patent families owned by the 362 companies in our sample before the companies received the first round of VC, 111 patent families (7.32 percent) contain patents with new IPC class combinations, i.e., radical inventions. These patent families are owned by 68 companies, i.e., by 18.78 percent of the companies in our sample.

Reputable Investor. The second key variable is the VC investor's reputation at the time of the VC investment. Following previous studies (e.g., Nahata, 2008; Colombo et al., 2019b), we measure investors' reputation as the ratio between the number of companies taken public by a VC investor in the 5 years prior to the focal investment and the total number of companies taken public by all VC investors in our sample in the same 5-year window. As this variable is highly skewed (skewness = 4.49), we create the dummy variable *Reputable Investor*, which equals 1 for the top 25 percent of the most successful VC investors.¹³

Control variables

Company-level factors. We control for the technological impact of a company's patent portfolio by counting the number of citations the patents in the portfolio received from subsequent patents prior to the focal company's first VC round. The citation variable is also built at the patent family level¹⁴. We use a logarithmic transformation of the number of citations received (*Forward Citations (log)*), as the distribution of the variable is highly skewed (skewness = 10.66). Moreover, we control for the company's average patent family size (*Average Patent Family Size*) as a measure of the geographical scope of protection (Putnam, 1996; Guellec and

¹³ In robustness checks, we document that our findings do not depend on the (admittedly arbitrary) choice of this threshold. We also use other measures of reputation and of invention radicalness.

¹⁴ We built alternative measures of companies' inventive performance: the number of distinct patent families a company has filed (portfolio size) and the number of patent families with at least one granted patent before a company's first financing round. These measures are highly correlated with the citation measure we use in our analysis (corr > 0.9). Our results remain robust when using these alternative measures of inventive performance.

van Pottelsberghe, 2000). We further control for companies' age in years (*Company Age*) and, using a number of dummies, their home countries (*Company Country*) and industry of operations (three-digit NACE classification, *Industry (NACE)*).

Investor-level factors. We control for a VC investor's experience in investing in companies in the life sciences. Dimov and Milanov (2010) show that VC investors tend to syndicate when the industry of the target company is novel to them, as they lack knowledge of market developments in the underlying industry. The variable *Industry Experience (log)* is the logarithm of a VC investor's number of investments in the industries under consideration in the five years prior to the focal investment. We take the logarithm of the industry experience variable, as the underlying distribution is highly skewed (skewness = 4.86).

Investment-level factors. We control for the (log of the) geographical distance between a company and a VC investor (*Distance (log)*). We further include the dummy variable *Same Country*, which equals 1 if the company and the VC investor are from the same country. Geographic distance and national borders have been shown to constitute serious barriers to the realization of VC ties (Chen et al., 2010; Colombo et al., 2019a).

Finally, we control for unobserved heterogeneity over time by including time fixed effects.

Empirical strategy

The formation of an investment tie between a young company and a VC investor is the result of a matching process in which companies looking for financing are screened by VC investors looking for investment opportunities. Companies with some characteristics (e.g., the level of radicalness) may constitute an interesting investment opportunity for certain types of VC investors (e.g., reputable investors), resulting in a realized investment tie, but not for others, resulting in an unrealized tie. To model this matching process, we analyze our data at the dyad level and compare the 436 realized VC investments relative to a counterfactual of unrealized investment dyads that could have formed (but did not). By using the dyad as a unit of analysis,

our econometric specification jointly considers how company- and investor-level characteristics are related to the probability of tie formation (for a similar approach in the context of VC investment tie formation, see, e.g., Dushnitsky and Shaver (2009), Colombo and Shafi (2016)). The condition for a potential but unrealized tie in a particular year is that both the company and the VC investor were observed in any realized investment tie in the focal year. The 362 companies and the 281 independent VC investors in our data formed 12,526 potential investor-company dyads that could have resulted in a realized investment tie. A total of 436 of the 12,526 potential investor-company dyads are realized investment ties, and 12,090 are unrealized ties. From the 436 realized investment ties, 103 are standalone ties, and 333 are syndicated ties.

Given the categorical nature of our dependent variable, we run multinomial logit models. To test our hypotheses, we analyze the conditional probabilities that VC investor j matches with company i in a standalone tie or in a syndicated tie in a given year. Hypothesis 1 predicts that a radical invention will be positively associated with the formation of a syndicated tie. In our empirical specification, this requires the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the formation of a syndicated tie to be positive and significant. Hypothesis 2 predicts that a radical invention will be positively associated with the formation of a tie with a reputable investor. In our empirical specification, this requires the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the formation of a tie with a *Reputable Investor* to be positive and significant.

We are aware that our empirical strategy does not allow for a causal interpretation of our results. Endogeneity might arise from unobserved heterogeneity. For example, companies with smarter and more creative founders may be more likely to generate radical inventions and be capable of attracting a larger number of VC investors. This could result in a higher likelihood of formation of syndicated ties. In addition, there may be alternative explanations for our findings. For example, since radical inventions have higher earning potential, companies with radical

inventions may be attractive for a larger number of VC investors, which again results in a greater likelihood of formation of syndicated ties.

In the following, we report our results. Afterwards, we provide robustness checks to test the validity of our measures and to rule out alternative explanations of our results.

RESULTS

Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics for all 12,526 potential investment ties. For 18.5 percent of the potential company-investor ties, the company has a patent filed for a radical invention. The companies are on average 3.1 years old when receiving their first round of VC. The companies' technology portfolios consisting of all inventions (patent families and patents granted or still pending) developed prior to funding received on average 10.6 citations and have an average patent family size of 9.6. The average VC investor in our sample of potential investor-company ties invested in 11.7 life science companies in the 5 years prior to the focal investment.

Table 2 reports the correlation matrix. The correlations between *Reputable Investor* and *Industry Experience (log)* (corr = 0.654) and between *Distance (log)* and *Same Country* (corr = -0.678) are high in magnitude. Variance inflation factors below 2, however, show that multicollinearity is not a concern.

[Insert Tables 1 and 2 here]

The results of a univariate analysis are presented in Table 3. Panel A reports the percentages of unrealized and realized (standalone, syndicated and total) investment ties with companies with at least one radical invention (*Radical Invention = 1*) or without a radical invention (*Radical Invention = 0*) at the time of the receipt of their first round of VC.

[Insert Table 3 here]

The results of the univariate analysis are in line with the relationships proposed in our hypotheses. The percentage of companies with at least one radical invention is higher in syndicated (24.9 percent) than in standalone (14.6 percent) or unrealized (18.4 percent) investment ties. In both cases, the difference is statistically significant (syndicated investment ties vs. standalone investment ties, Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test: $z = -2.199$; $p = 0.028$; syndicated investment ties vs. unrealized investment ties, Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test: $z = -3.036$; $p = 0.002$). In panels B and C of Table 3, we distinguish ties with reputable (*Reputable Investor = 1*) and non-reputable (*Reputable Investor = 0*) VC investors. The overall percentage of realized ties involving companies with at least one radical invention is higher for reputable VC investors (29.3 percent) than for non-reputable VC investors (20.3 percent). This difference is statistically significant at the 10 percent level (Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test: $z = -1.917$; $p = 0.055$). Quite interestingly, this difference is entirely attributable to syndicated ties, while the percentage of realized standalone ties with companies having developed one or more radical inventions out of all realized standalone ties is lower for reputable investors than for non-reputable ones, even if the difference is not significant.

Table 4 presents the results of a multinomial logit analysis, with standard errors clustered by investor. We use unrealized ties as our reference group (i.e., *Dealtype = 0*). Model 1 only contains the control variables. Model 2 introduces our key explanatory variables *Radical Invention* and *Reputable Investor*. Model 3 adds their interaction term. Table 5 provides the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* on the likelihood of an unrealized, standalone and syndicated tie based on the results from Model 2 and Model 3.

Model 1 (Table 4) shows that the log-odds of forming a syndicated tie to not forming any tie significantly increase ($\beta = 0.17$; $p = 0.000$) with an increase in the number of forward citations received by the technology portfolio (Forward Citations). In addition, a larger number of investments in life science companies in the last 5 years before the focal investment (Industry

Experience) leads to an increase of the log-odds of a syndicated tie compared to not forming any tie ($\beta = 0.08$; $p = 0.036$). The distance between the focal VC investor and the focal company (Distance) significantly decreases both the log-odds of forming a standalone tie ($\beta = -0.26$; $p = 0.000$) and the log-odds of forming a syndicated tie ($\beta = -0.19$; $p = 0.000$) compared to not forming any tie. Conversely, being located in the same country (Same Country) significantly increases both the log-odds of forming a standalone ($\beta = 2.85$; $p = 0.000$) and the log-odds of forming a syndicated tie ($\beta = 2.79$; $p = 0.000$) compared to not forming any tie.

Model 2 introduces our key variables of interest. The results from Table 4 show that the log-odds of forming a syndicated tie relative to not forming any tie increase by 0.38 ($p = 0.022$) if the company has at least one radical invention, while the log-odds of having a standalone tie relative to an unrealized tie do not change significantly. The log-odds of the control variables are consistent with Model 1 in terms of their significance level.

In multinomial logit models, a positive coefficient of an explanatory variable does not necessarily correspond to an increase in the probability of a particular outcome category. Hence, to test Hypothesis 1, we calculate the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the likelihood of forming a syndicated tie based on the econometric specification of Model 2. The estimated probability of forming a syndicated tie for companies without any radical invention is 2.5 percent. As reported in Table 5 (Model 2), the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* indicates that this probability increases by 1.0 percentage point ($p = 0.034$) if the company has one or more radical inventions, which represents an increase of 40 percent. Our results hence support Hypothesis 1.

[Insert Tables 4 and 5 here]

To test Hypothesis 2, we calculate the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* based on the estimates of Model 3, while differentiating between less reputable investors (*Reputable Investor* = 0) and more reputable ones (*Reputable Investor* = 1). Table 5 shows that for non-reputable

investors (Model 3-I), the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the formation of either a standalone tie or a syndicated tie is not significant at standard significance levels. For reputable investors (Model 3-II), the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the probability of forming an investment tie—regardless of whether it is a standalone or syndicated tie—is positive, significant ($p = 0.013$) and of large magnitude (2.4 percentage points). Quite interestingly, this effect is entirely attributable to syndicated ties. Indeed, the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the likelihood of forming a syndicated investment tie is highly significant ($p = 0.004$) and equal to 2.8 percentage points. Taking the probability of 2 percent for the formation of a syndicated tie with a reputable investor without the presence of a radical invention as a reference point, an increase in this probability from 2 to 4.8 percent when the company has at least one radical invention in its technology portfolio equals a 140 percent increase. We do not find a significant association between *Radical Invention* and the formation of a standalone tie.

Overall, the results of Model 3 do not fully confirm Hypothesis 2, according to which radical inventions increase the probability of a company forming a tie with a reputable investor. Our findings indicate that this positive association is confined to syndicated ties.

ROBUSTNESS CHECKS

To assess the robustness of our results, we use alternative measures for our key explanatory variables and apply different restrictions to define company-investor dyads that are at risk of realizing an investment tie. The results are summarized in Tables A1, A2, A3 and A4 in the Appendix. In addition, we test the assumption of the independence of irrelevant alternatives (Table A5 in the Appendix) and control for unobserved characteristics at the company- and investor-level (Table A6 in the Appendix).

As a first robustness check, we use an alternative measure for radical inventions (*Radical Invention (global scale)*) that is built based on patent applications filed with any of the patent offices worldwide after 1980, instead of just with the EPO, USPTO, and WIPO. The advantage

of adding national patent data is an increase in the geographical scope covered by our measure. The disadvantage is that differences between national patent legislations decrease the comparability of the data. The results (Appendix—Table A1) are fully in line with those of our main analysis, although the magnitude of the effects and the statistical significance are lower in Model 4 than in Model 2.

As a second robustness check, we show that our results remain unchanged independently of how we categorize reputable and non-reputable VC investors. First, our results do not depend on the arbitrary choice of the 75th percentile as a cutoff point to distinguish between reputable and non-reputable investors. In Model 6 in Table A2, we show the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* on the likelihood of an unrealized, standalone and syndicated tie at different points of the reputation distribution. In particular, we estimate a multinomial model by using a continuous measure for investor reputation (*Investor Reputation (continuous)*) and then calculate marginal effects at the median and the 75th, 90th, and 95th percentiles of this variable.¹⁵ Both the magnitude and the statistical significance of the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the likelihood of forming a syndicated tie increase as *Investor Reputation (continuous)* increases. Furthermore, we build an alternative reputation measure considering a 3-year instead of a 5-year period prior to the focal investment (Model 7). We also measure VC investors' reputation as the share of investments made (instead of companies taken public) by a given investor during the 5 years prior to the focal investment out of all investments made by all VC investors in our sample in the same period (Model 8; see Pollock et al., 2015). To distinguish reputable and nonreputable VC investors, we thus create two dummies: *Reputable Investor (#IPO 3 years)* and *Reputable Investor (#investments 5 years)* that equal 1 for VC investors that

¹⁵ As mentioned earlier, the underlying distribution of investor reputation is highly skewed. The 50th percentile equals the 1st percentile. Thus, we focus on cutoff points equal to or greater than the median.

lie in the top quartile of the underlying reputation distributions. Again, the results are consistent with our main regressions.

Third, we use alternative estimation strategies. In our main estimates, we cluster standard errors by investor to deal with the problem of nonindependence across cases, as each company and each VC investor enter the analysis repeatedly. Models 9 and 10 in Table A3 in the Appendix show the estimations when clustering standard errors by company. The statistical significance of the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* are in line with our main results.

Moreover, we use alternative strategies to build the counterfactual of unrealized ties. Previously, we used all possible dyads between companies that were financed in a given year and all VC investors that were active in that year, which resulted in a dataset with 436 realized ties (3.48 percent) and 12,090 unrealized ties (96.52 percent). In this data structure, realized ties are therefore rare events. This might cause underestimation of the likelihood of these events when applying logistic regression (King and Zeng, 2001). Thus, we apply two strategies to address this issue. First, when building the counterfactual of unrealized ties, we match companies and investors based on the investment year and the country of the company. Accordingly, each company is matched with VC investors who were active in the home country of the focal company and in the same investment year. This alternative matching procedure resulted in a lower number of unrealized ties (2,736 instead of 12,090 ties), but the results are consistent with our main regressions (see Models 11 and 12 in Table A3 in the Appendix). The likelihood of forming a syndicated tie, for instance, increases by 3.7 percentage points ($p = 0.036$) in the case of a radical invention, which represents an increase in the likelihood of forming a syndicated tie by 38 percent (from 0.097 to 0.133). Second, we apply choice-based sampling by randomly selecting ties within our sample of counterfactuals but keeping all realized ties (King and Zeng, 2001). We followed Sorenson and Stuart (2008) and randomly draw, for each realized tie, either 10 or 5 unrealized ties from the original counterfactual used

in our main analysis. Table A4 shows the results of 1,000 simulations of Model 2 and Model 3, applying random sampling without replacement. Our main result that the marginal effect of *Radical Invention* on the formation of an investment tie is entirely attributable to syndicated ties is confirmed.

Fourth, a stringent assumption of multinomial logit models is the independence of irrelevant alternatives. This assumption requires the estimated results to be robust against the inclusion or exclusion of outcome categories (e.g., Hausman and McFadden, 1984). We compare the estimated coefficients of *Radical Invention* and *Reputable Investor* from a full multinomial logit model (without any control variables) including all outcome categories of *Dealtype* with the coefficients from two logistic regressions excluding either standalone or syndicated ties (Models 13 to 15 in Table A5). We apply suest-based Hausman tests to assess the differences in coefficients¹⁶. When we exclude one outcome category, the results do not show any systematic difference in the coefficients compared to those of the multinomial logit model (full model vs. model without syndicated ties: $p = 0.775$; full model vs. model without standalone ties: $p = 0.745$). Thus, the null hypothesis of independent alternatives cannot be rejected.

Last, our results might be driven by unobserved characteristics of companies or investors. For example, it could be that higher-quality companies are more likely both to produce radical inventions and to attract more reputable investors. To address these concerns, we run a conditional multinomial logit model that controls for latent company characteristics (Model 16 in Table A6) and two conditional binary logit models that control for latent VC investor characteristics (Models 17 and 18 in the same table) through fixed effects¹⁷. As the

¹⁶ The classic Hausman (1978) test may be undefined because the estimated clustered standard errors do not satisfy the asymptotic properties of the test (Gourieroux and Monfort, 1995).

¹⁷ When conditioning on the investor, the multinomial logit estimation computed by the *femlogit* Stata package (Pforr, 2014) does not converge. Hence, we rely on two separate logistic regressions that compare unrealized to standalone ties (Model 17) and unrealized to syndicated ties (Model 18). Begg and Gray (1984) show that under the assumption of the independence of irrelevant alternatives, consistent (albeit inefficient) estimates can be obtained by estimating separate logit models instead of a single multinomial model.

maximization of a conditional log-likelihood does not produce an estimation of fixed effects (i.e., unobserved heterogeneity with regard to the company or investor), computation of marginal effects is not adequate (Greene and Zhang, 2019). Thus, Table A6 reports the changes in the log-odds. Regardless of whether we condition on company or VC investor, the interaction between *Radical Invention* and *Reputable Investor* increases the log-odds of forming a syndicated tie to not forming any tie. The results when controlling for unobserved heterogeneity at the company- or investor-level are in line with the main results.

Additional Analyses to Rule out Alternative Explanations

A possible alternative explanation of our results is related to the geography of companies with radical inventions and VC inventors. Companies with radical inventions are heavily reliant on external funding to further develop their inventions and thus might intentionally choose to locate themselves close to areas with a high density of VC investors (so-called VC hubs, such as London and Paris) to increase the likelihood of receiving funding (De Prijcker et al., 2019). In these areas, a large number of VC investors are potentially attracted by these companies. To reduce competition and the associated risk of overpaying, these VC investors may decide to collude by syndicating their investments. This may lead to a positive association between the *Radical Invention* dummy and the likelihood of observing a syndicated tie. In addition, highly reputable investors tend to be located in VC hubs.¹⁸ Colocation with companies with radical inventions may generate a positive interaction term in our estimates between the *Radical Innovation* and *Reputable Investor* dummies. In sum, if companies with radical inventions are located in VC hubs and VC hubs are characterized by higher competition among VC investors for attractive deals and a greater presence of reputable investors, this may drive our results.

¹⁸ For example, out of the 25 VC investors with the highest reputation (measured at the end of 2014) included in our sample, 10 are located in the London or Paris metropolitan areas, the two largest VC hubs in Europe.

To rule out this alternative explanation, we compare the share of companies with one or more radical inventions that are located in VC hubs ($VC\ Hub = 1$) to the share of companies with one or more radical inventions that are located outside VC hubs ($VC\ Hub = 0$). The results of this univariate analysis are presented in Table A7 in the Appendix. Panel A reports the percentages of companies with one or more radical inventions or without any radical inventions that are located within or outside the metropolitan areas of London or Paris.¹⁹ Interestingly, the percentage of companies with at least one radical invention that are located in London or Paris (15 percent) is lower than the percentage of those outside these VC hubs (19.25 percent), although this difference is not statistically significant (Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test: $z = 0.649$; $p = 0.516$). In panels B and C, we consider the 5 and 10 largest VC hubs in Europe according to VICO in terms of the number of investment deals. Again, we do not find any significant evidence that companies with radical inventions are more likely to be located in VC hubs than those without radical inventions (Panel B, Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test: $z = -0.397$; $p = 0.691$; Panel C: $z = 0.333$; $p = 0.739$). As a consequence, it is not surprising that we still find a significant correlation between *Radical Invention* and the formation of a syndicated tie with a reputable VC investor if we drop from our sample the companies located in the London and Paris metropolitan areas.²⁰

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to theoretically examine signals that convey positive and negative information at the same time and the ways in which the tension created by such signals can be resolved. Accordingly, we empirically analyzed how VC investors react to signals that carry negative, in addition to positive, information, in our study of patents protecting radical inventions.

¹⁹ In our sample, 11 percent of companies are located in London or Paris.

²⁰ The results from these regressions are available from the authors upon request.

We started by noting that the existing literature on signals has dealt with multiple signals, which may overburden a receiver characterized by bounded rationality (Pollock et al., 2010; Stern et al., 2014). A small number of studies have dealt with multiple conflicting signals (Drover et al., 2018). However, to our knowledge, existing work has, so far, disregarded conflicting information contained in a single signal. These signals, which we refer to as signals with a dark side, are highly relevant. Whereas psychological tension can be avoided in the case of multiple signals by focusing on selected signals (while ignoring the rest), it cannot be straightforwardly avoided when conflicting information is contained in a single signal. Hence, there is a need to resolve or reduce psychological tension. Based on signaling theory and balance theory, we suggest that there are two options to move from tension to a balanced state: (1) actions to reduce or eliminate tension and (2) cognitive reorganization, i.e., a reevaluation of the situation (Opp, 1984).

Our results show that young companies with radical inventions (i.e., signals with a dark side) are attractive investment targets for reputable investors but not for non-reputable ones and that these reputable investors syndicate their investments. Hence, the dark side of the signal leads to both a reevaluation of the information content of the signal (cognitive reorganization) and an action to reduce or eliminate the tension at the same time. In other words, VC investors use both possible mechanisms at the same time to reduce the tension resulting from a signal with a dark side.

Our findings contribute to signaling theory in several ways. First, we add to the theory by introducing the “dark side” of a signal, i.e., we theorize on signals that convey positive and negative information. Furthermore, we show how receivers react to a positive signal that has a dark side and highlight the importance of the characteristics of signal receivers. The existing literature has so far only addressed the receivers of multiple contradictory signals (Vanacker and Forbes, 2016).

Second, we show that the dark side of a signal matters for decision makers and that it can decrease and possibly even neutralize the positive information effect of the signal. We show this in the context of VC investors who decide whether and under which conditions to invest in young companies with patents protecting radical inventions. We find that only reputable VC investors with a track record of previous successful investments are willing to accept the dark side of the signal and invest. The result that non-reputable VC investors are deterred by the dark side of a signal and abstain from investing echoes the prediction of Drover et al. (2018) that in the presence of multiple incongruent and similarly strong signals, firms may abstain from forming a judgment at all. This renders a signal useless.

Third, we show that by reevaluating the signal and resorting to suitable action (syndication), receivers with selected characteristics, in our case, reputable VC investors, can alleviate the negative effects of the signal's dark side. The receivers ultimately disregard the dark side of the signal and, thus, fully benefit from the positive information attached to it—in our case, the high potential returns associated with investing in companies that have developed radical innovations.

We also contribute to the entrepreneurial finance literature. Signals such as patents allow young innovative companies to alleviate the information asymmetries that make it difficult for them to raise external equity (Hsu and Ziedonis, 2008). We add to this literature by showing that these signals may have a dark side. The negative information attached to the signal is more or less damaging depending on signal receivers' characteristics—in our case, the reputation of VC investors—that influence their perception or interpretation of the information content of the signal. We also show that syndication is an effective action allowing VC investors (at least reputable ones) to reduce the risk associated with the dark side of the signal. In so doing, we highlight boundary conditions that make incongruent signals more or less effective in alleviating the abovementioned information asymmetries. These results help us better

understand the determinants of a good match being made between VC investors and young companies looking for external financing.

Our study has interesting managerial implications for entrepreneurs. Highly innovative ideas resulting in radical inventions may be punished by VC investors, since non-reputable investors and investors without syndication partners, in particular, may not want to take on the risk involved in such an investment. However, young companies are heavily reliant on external financing. Due to the high risk associated with radical inventions, equity financing is usually the only available source of finance. Hence, the creators of radical inventions have to understand the impact of the signal they send and the target group of potentially interested investors to increase their chances of obtaining external financing.

Finally, our study has implications for policy makers as well. Radical inventions are of particular interest since they are “driving forces of technological, industrial and societal change” (Schoenmakers and Duysters, 2010: 1052), and they have the potential to enhance private and social welfare (Ahuja and Lampert, 2001; Harhoff et al., 1999; Trajtenberg, 1990). If the signals sent by patents on radical inventions are not effective, this could lead to an underinvestment problem in radical invention. A possible solution to this problem, in addition to public support (e.g., Bertoni et al., 2019b; Guerini and Quas 2016), could be alternative financing mechanisms such as crowdfunding. Otherwise, potentially break-through inventions may never be developed or brought to market, i.e., turned into innovations.

With respect to the limitations of our study, we recognize that in our results, endogeneity might arise from (time-varying) unobserved heterogeneity. Therefore, caution is required in interpreting our results as indicating causal links. For instance, we cannot rule out that time-varying unobserved characteristics of investors (e.g., overconfidence of investment managers) explain the differences between reputable and non-reputable investors when screening companies with radical inventions. However, our strong theoretical foundation, the robustness

tests (the conditional multinomial logit model that controls for unobserved company characteristics and the conditional binary logit models that control for unobserved VC investor characteristics), and the fact that we can rule out one of the seemingly most obvious alternative explanations for our findings make us confident that our results are reliable and that our interpretation of the results is correct. Nevertheless, future research that takes into account more fine-grained information is needed to further alleviate causality concerns.

Furthermore, although our results are robust to different matching strategies and counterfactuals, we acknowledge that we do not observe which young innovative companies had been evaluated and screened by which VC investors. We therefore welcome studies that have more detailed data on funded and unfunded companies that approached the same VC investor.

We also recognize that our study is (for the reasons explained in our paper) restricted to one industry. This may limit the generalizability of our results. Although we are confident that our results hold in other environments, future research should examine the dark side of signals in other industries and possibly also in contexts other than entrepreneurship.

Another promising avenue of research is to examine other contingency factors. Extending our knowledge of the dark side of signals can have an important impact on our understanding of signals and help further develop one of the most respected and most highly cited theories in strategy research.

REFERENCES

- Adejumo G, Duimering PR, Zhong Z. 2008. A balance theory approach to group problem solving. *Social Networks* **30**(1): 83-99.
- Ahuja G, Lampert CM. 2001. Entrepreneurship in the large corporation: A longitudinal study of how established firms create breakthrough inventions. *Strategic Management Journal* **22**(6-7): 521-543.
- Anderson CR. 1976. Coping behaviors as intervening mechanisms in the inverted-U stress-performance relationship. *Journal of Applied Psychology* **61**(1): 30-34.
- Atuahene-Gima K. 2005. Resolving the capability—rigidity paradox in new product innovation. *Journal of Marketing* **69**(4): 61-83.
- Azoulay P, Graff Zivin JS, Manso G. 2011. Incentives and creativity: evidence from the academic life sciences. *The RAND Journal of Economics* **42**(3): 527-554.
- Bayar O, Chemmanur TJ, Liu MH. 2019. How to Motivate Fundamental Innovation: Optimal Interactions between Entrepreneurs, Venture Capitalists, and the Government. Venture Capitalists, and the Government, Discussion Paper, https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/Papers.cfm?abstract_id=2799490.
- Begg CB, Gray R. 1984. Calculation of Polychotomous Logistic Regression Parameters Using Individualized Regressions. *Biometrika*: 11-18.
- Bergh DD, Connelly BL, Ketchen DJ, Shannon LM. 2014. Signalling theory and equilibrium in strategic management research: An assessment and a research agenda. *Journal of Management Studies* **51**(8): 1334-1360.
- Bertoni F, Colombo MG, Quas A. 2015. The patterns of venture capital investment in Europe. *Small Business Economic* **45**(3): 543-560.
- Bertoni F, Colombo MG, Quas A, Tenca F 2019a. The changing patterns of venture capital investments in Europe. *Journal of Industrial and Business Economics* **46**(2): 229-250.
- Bertoni F, Colombo MG, Quas A. 2019b. The role of governmental venture capital in the venture capital ecosystem: An organizational ecology perspective. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice* **43**(3): 611-628.
- Brander JA, Amit R, Antweiler W. 2002. Venture-capital syndication: Improved venture selection vs. the value-added hypothesis. *Journal of Economics & Management Strategy* **11**(3): 423-452.
- Bygrave WD. 1987. Syndicated investments by venture capital firms: A networking perspective. *Journal of Business Venturing* **2**(2): 139-154.
- Carpenter RE, Petersen BC 2002. Capital market imperfections, high-tech investment, and new equity financing. *Economic Journal* **112**: F54-F72.
- Chen H, Gompers P, Kovner A, Lerner J. 2010. Buy local? The geography of venture capital. *Journal of Urban Economics* **67**(1): 90-102.
- Cohen WM, Walsh JP. 2002. Public research, patents and implications for industrial R&D in the drug, biotechnology, semiconductor and computer industries. Capitalizing on new needs and new opportunities: Government-industry partnerships in biotechnology and information technologies, 223-243.
- Colombo MG, D'Adda D, Quas A. 2019a. The geography of venture capital and entrepreneurial ventures' demand for external equity. *Research Policy* **48**(5): 1150-1170.
- Colombo MG, Meoli M, Vismara S 2019b. Signaling in science-based IPOs: The combined effect of affiliation with prestigious universities, underwriters, and venture capitalists. *Journal of Business Venturing* **34**(1): 141-177.

- Colombo MG, Shafi K. 2016. Swimming with sharks in Europe: When are they dangerous and what can new ventures do to defend themselves? *Strategic Management Journal* **37**(11): 2307-2322.
- Connelly BL, Certo ST, Ireland RD, Reutzel CR. 2011. Signaling Theory: A Review and Assessment. *Journal of Management* **37**: 39-67.
- Dahlin KB, Behrens DM. 2005. When is an invention really radical? Defining and measuring technological radicalness. *Research Policy* **34**(5): 717-737.
- De Vet JM, Scott AJ. 1992. The Southern Californian medical device industry: Innovation, new firm formation, and location. *Research Policy* **21**(2): 145-161.
- Deeds DL, Decarolis D, Coombs JE. 1997. The impact of firm-specific capabilities on the amount of capital raised in an initial public offering: Evidence from the biotechnology industry. *Journal of Business Venturing* **12**(1): 31-46.
- Deeds DL, Mang PY, Frandsen ML. 2004. The influence of firms' and industries' legitimacy on the flow of capital into high-technology ventures. *Strategic Organization* **2**(1): 9-34.
- Denis DJ. 2004. Entrepreneurial finance: an overview of the issues and evidence. *Journal of Corporate Finance* **10**(2): 301-326.
- De Prijcker S, Manigart S, Collewaert V, Vanacker T. 2019. Relocation to get venture capital: a resource dependence perspective. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice* **43**(4): 697-724.
- Dewar RD, Dutton JE. 1986. The adoption of radical and incremental innovations: An empirical analysis. *Management Science* **32**(11): 1422-1433.
- Dimov D, Milanov H. 2010. The interplay of need and opportunity in venture capital investment syndication. *Journal of Business Venturing* **25**(4): 331-348.
- Drover W, Wood MS, Corbett AC. 2018. Toward a cognitive view of signalling theory: individual attention and signal set interpretation. *Journal of Management Studies* **55**(2): 209-231.
- Dushnitsky G, Shaver JM. 2009. Limitations to interorganizational knowledge acquisition: The paradox of corporate venture capital. *Strategic Management Journal* **30**(10): 1045-1064.
- Elitzur R, Gaviols A. 2003. Contracting, signaling, and moral hazard: A model of entrepreneurs, "angels," and venture capitalists. *Journal of Business Venturing* **18**: 709-725.
- Fleming L. 2001. Recombinant uncertainty in technological search. *Management Science* **47**(1): 117-132.
- Fleming L, Mingo S, Chen D. 2007. Collaborative brokerage, generative creativity, and creative success. *Administrative Science Quarterly* **52**(3): 443-475.
- Fombrun CJ. 1996. Reputation, Harvard Business School Press. Boston, MA.
- Gourieroux C, Monfort A. 1995. Statistics and econometric models (Vol. 1). Cambridge University Press.
- Greene W, Zhang Q. 2019. Nonlinear and Related Panel Data Models. In Panel Data Econometrics (pp. 45-96). Academic Press.
- Guellec D, van Pottelsberghe de la Potterie B. 2000. Applications, grants and the value of patent. *Economics Letters* **69**(1): 109-114.
- Guerini M, Quas A. 2016. Governmental venture capital in Europe: Screening and certification. *Journal of Business Venturing* **31**(2): 175-195.
- Hall BH, Lerner J. 2010. The financing of R&D and innovation. In Hall, B. H. and N. Rosenberg (eds.), Handbook of the Economics of Innovation. Elsevier-North Holland.

- Harhoff D. 2016. Patent quality and examination in Europe. *American Economic Review* **106**(5): 193-197.
- Harhoff D, Narin F, Scherer M, Vopel K. 1999. Citation frequency and the value of patented inventions. *Review of Economics and Statistics* **81**(3): 511–515.
- Hausman JA. 1978. Specification tests in econometrics. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*: 1251-1271.
- Hausman J, McFadden D. 1984. Specification tests for the multinomial logit model. *Econometrica: Journal of the Econometric Society*: 1219-1240.
- Heider F. 1958. *The Psychology of Interpersonal Relations*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Higgins MC, Gulati R. 2006. Stacking the deck: The effects of top management backgrounds on investor decisions. *Strategic Management Journal* **27**(1): 1-25.
- Hoenen S, Kolympiris C, Schoenmakers W, Kalaitzandonakes N. 2014. The diminishing signaling value of patents between early rounds of venture capital financing. *Research Policy* **43**(6): 956-989.
- Hoenig D, Henkel J. 2015. Quality signals? The role of patents, alliances, and team experience in venture capital financing. *Research Policy* **44**(5): 1049-1064.
- Honeysett JM, Metheny R. 2012. The importance of matching talented leadership with the growth stage of your life-sciences company. *Nature biotechnology* **30**(6): 563.
- Hsu DH. 2007. Experienced entrepreneurial founders, organizational capital, and venture capital funding. *Research Policy* **36**(5): 722-741.
- Hsu DH, Ziedonis RH. 2008. Patents as quality signals for entrepreneurial ventures. *Academy of Management Proceedings* **2008**(1): 1-6.
- Janney JJ, Folta TB. 2003. Signaling through private equity placements and its impact on the valuation of biotechnology firms. *Journal of Business Venturing* **18**(3): 361-380.
- Junkunc MT. 2007. Managing radical innovation: The importance of specialized knowledge in the biotech revolution. *Journal of Business Venturing* **22**: 388-411.
- Kaplan SN, Strömberg PE. 2004. Characteristics, contracts, and actions: Evidence from venture capitalist analyses. *The Journal of Finance* **59**(5): 2177-2210.
- King, G, Zeng L. 2001. Logistic regression in rare events data. *Political Analysis* **9**(2): 137-163.
- Kolympiris C, Kalaitzandonakes N, Miller D. 2014. Public funds and local biotechnology firm creation. *Research Policy* **43**: 121–137.
- Lee PM, Pollock TG, Jin K. 2011. The contingent value of venture capitalist reputation. *Strategic Organization* **9**(1): 33-69.
- Lerner J. 1994. The syndication of venture capital investments. *Financial Management*: 16-27.
- McDermott CM, O'Connor GC. 2002. Managing radical innovation: an overview of emergent strategy issues. *Journal of Product Innovation Management* **19**(6): 424-438.
- Nahata R. 2008. Venture capital reputation and investment performance. *Journal of Financial Economics* **90**(2): 127-151.
- Nanda R, Rhodes-Kropf M. 2013. Investment cycles and startup innovation. *Journal of Financial Economics* **110**(2): 403-418.
- Nasto B. 2008. Chasing biotech across Europe. *Nature Biotechnology* **26**(3): 283-288.
- Nofsinger JR, Wang W. 2011. Determinants of start-up firm external financing worldwide. *Journal of Banking & Finance* **35**(9): 2282-2294.
- Opp KD. 1984. Balance theory: Progress and stagnation of a social psychological theory. *Philosophy of the Social Sciences* **14**(1): 27-49.

- Petkova AP, Wadhwa A, Yao X, Jain S. 2014. Reputation and decision making under ambiguity: a study of US venture capital firms' investments in the emerging clean energy sector. *Academy of Management Journal* **57**(2): 422-448.
- Pfarrer MD, Pollock TG, Rindova VP. 2010. A tale of two assets: The effects of firm reputation and celebrity on earnings surprises and investors' reactions. *Academy of Management Journal* **53**(5): 1131-1152.
- Pfarr K. 2014. femlogit—implementation of the multinomial logit model with fixed effects. *The Stata Journal* **14**(4): 847-862.
- Pollock TG, Chen G, Jackson EM, Hambrick DC. 2010. How much prestige is enough? Assessing the value of multiple types of high-status affiliates for young firms. *Journal of Business Venturing* **25**(1): 6-23.
- Pollock TG, Lee PM, Jin K, Lashley K. 2015. (Un) tangled: Exploring the asymmetric coevolution of new venture capital firms' reputation and status. *Administrative Science Quarterly* **60**(3): 482-517.
- Pollock TG, Porac JF, Wade JB. 2004. Constructing deal networks: Brokers as network “architects” in the US IPO market and other examples. *Academy of Management Review* **29**(1): 50-72.
- Putnam J. 1996. *The Value of International Patent Rights*. Yale.
- Raisch S, Birkinshaw J. 2008. Organizational ambidexterity: Antecedents, outcomes, and moderators. *Journal of Management* **34**(3): 375-409.
- Rindova VP, Fombrun CJ. 1999. Constructing competitive advantage: the role of firm–constituent interactions. *Strategic Management Journal* **20**(8): 691-710.
- Rubera G, Kirca AH. 2012. Firm innovativeness and its performance outcomes: A meta-analytic review and theoretical integration. *Journal of Marketing* **76**(3): 130-147.
- Schoenmakers W, Duysters G. 2010. The technological origins of radical inventions. *Research Policy* **39**(8): 1051-1059.
- Schumpeter J. 1934. *Capitalism, socialism, and democracy*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Shane S, Stuart T. 2002. Organizational endowments and the performance of university start-ups. *Management Science* **48**(1): 154-170.
- Shannon CE, Weaver W. 1949 *The mathematical theory of communication*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press. 117 p; <http://math.harvard.edu/~ctm/home/text/others/shannon/entropy/entropy.pdf>.
- Simon HA. 1991. Bounded rationality and organizational learning. *Organization Science* **2**(1): 125-134.
- Spence M. 1973. Job market signaling. *Quarterly Journal of Economics* **87**: 355-374.
- Spence M. 2002. Signaling in retrospect and the informational structure of markets. *American Economic Review* **92**: 434-459.
- Steigenberger N, Wilhelm H. 2018. Extending signaling theory to rhetorical signals: Evidence from crowdfunding. *Organization Science* **29**(3): 529-546.
- Stern I, Dukerich JM, Zajac E. 2014. Unmixed signals: How reputation and status affect alliance formation. *Strategic Management Journal* **35**(4): 512-531.
- Stiglitz JE. 2000. The contributions of the economics of information to twentieth century economics. *Quarterly Journal of Economics* **115**: 1441-1478.
- Stiglitz JE. 2002. Information and the change in the paradigm in economics. *American Economic Review* **92**: 460-501.

- Stuart TE, Hoang H, Hybels RC. 1999. Interorganizational endorsements and the performance of entrepreneurial ventures. *Administrative Science Quarterly* **44**(2): 315-349.
- Trajtenberg M. 1990. Economic Analysis of Product Innovation: The Case of CT Scanners. Harvard University Press: Cambridge, MA.
- Vanacker T, Forbes DP. 2016. Disentangling the multiple effects of affiliate reputation on resource attraction in new firms. *Organization Science* **27**(6): 1525-1547.
- Sorenson O, Stuart TE. 2008. Bringing the context back in: Settings and the search for syndicate partners in venture capital investment networks. *Administrative Science Quarterly* **53**(2): 266-294.
- Verhoeven D, Bakker J, Veugelers R. 2016. Measuring technological novelty with patent-based indicators. *Research Policy* **45**(3): 707-723.
- Wright M, Lockett A. 2003. The structure and management of alliances: syndication in the venture capital industry. *Journal of Management Studies* **40**(8): 2073-2102.
- Zucker LG, Darby MR, Brewer MB. 1998. Intellectual human capital and the birth of the U.S. biotechnology enterprise. *American Economic Review* **88**: 290-306.

TABLES

Table 1 - Descriptive statistics ($N = 12,526$)

	mean	sd	min	max
Dependent variable				
Unrealized Tie	0.965		0	1
Standalone Tie	0.008		0	1
Syndicated Tie	0.027		0	1
Independent variables				
Radical Invention	0.185		0	1
Reputable Investor	0.248		0	1
Forward Citations	10.613	53.154	0	672
Average Patent Family Size	9.750	6.188	1	67
Company Age	3.083	2.630	0	10
Industry Experience	11.673	25.197	0	255
Distance	2,066.232	2,403.689	0	12,223.653
Same Country	0.160		0	1
Period 2003-2006	0.374		0	1
Period 2007-2010	0.399		0	1
Period 2011-2015	0.227		0	1

Note: We report descriptive statistics for the original specifications of our measures, i.e. before their logarithmic transformation (Forward Citations, Industry Experience, Distance). For the dependent categorical variable (Dealttype), we created three dummy variables indicating the respective outcome category.

Table 2 - Bivariate correlations ($N = 12,526$)

	Independent variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Radical Invention	1							
2	Reputable Investor	-0.005	1						
3	Forward Citations (log)	0.354	-0.003	1					
4	Average Patent Family Size	0.002	0.031	0.033	1				
5	Company Age	0.099	0.009	0.293	-0.094	1			
6	Industry Experience (log)	-0.002	0.654	0.006	0.021	0.008	1		
7	Distance (log)	0.010	0.010	0.011	-0.007	0.009	0.027	1	
8	Same Country	0.006	-0.012	0.032	-0.004	0.030	-0.028	-0.678	1

Table 3 - Frequency table

	Unrealized Ties		Realized Ties					
			Standalone Ties		Syndicated Ties		Total	
Panel A								
<i>All potential ties</i>								
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Radical Invention = 0	9,869	81.63	88	85.44	250	75.08	338	77.52
Radical Invention = 1	2,221	18.37	15	14.56	83	24.92	98	22.48
Total	12,090	100.00	103	100.00	333	100.00	436	100.00
Panel B								
<i>All potential ties with reputable VC investors (Reputable Investor = 1)</i>								
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Radical Invention = 0	2,465	82.19	23	92.00	52	64.20	75	70.75
Radical Invention = 1	534	17.81	2	8.00	29	35.80	31	29.25
Total	2,999	100.00	25	100.00	81	100.00	106	100.00
Panel C								
<i>All potential ties with non-reputable VC investors (Reputable Investor = 0)</i>								
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
Radical Invention = 0	7,404	81.44	65	83.33	198	78.57	263	79.70
Radical Invention = 1	1,687	18.56	13	16.67	54	21.43	67	20.30
Total	9,091	100.00	78	100.00	252	100.00	330	100.00

Table 4 - Results of the multinomial regressions

Outcome reference: Unrealized Tie vs.	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3	
	Standalone Tie	Syndicated Tie	Standalone Tie	Syndicated Tie	Standalone Tie	Syndicated Tie
Radical Invention			0.013 [0.966] (0.296)	0.384 [0.022] (0.167)	0.119 [0.710] (0.320)	0.146 [0.445] (0.191)
Reputable Investor			-0.105 [0.736] (0.310)	-0.070 [0.561] (0.120)	-0.030 [0.928] (0.334)	-0.320 [0.032] (0.149)
Radical Invention X Reputable Investor					-0.625 [0.417] (0.770)	0.885 [0.007] (0.330)
Forward Citations (log)	-0.139 [0.080] (0.080)	0.173 [0.000] (0.047)	-0.141 [0.096] (0.085)	0.131 [0.013] (0.052)	-0.138 [0.101] (0.084)	0.131 [0.012] (0.053)
Average Patent Family Size	0.014 [0.347] (0.015)	0.015 [0.159] (0.010)	0.014 [0.341] (0.015)	0.016 [0.133] (0.010)	0.014 [0.354] (0.015)	0.016 [0.123] (0.010)
Company Age	0.039 [0.365] (0.043)	-0.009 [0.702] (0.024)	0.039 [0.355] (0.043)	-0.008 [0.733] (0.024)	0.038 [0.365] (0.042)	-0.008 [0.748] (0.024)
Industry Experience (log)	0.079 [0.244] (0.068)	0.077 [0.036] (0.037)	0.101 [0.282] (0.094)	0.089 [0.035] (0.042)	0.098 [0.296] (0.094)	0.091 [0.029] (0.042)
Distance (log)	-0.258 [0.000] (0.074)	-0.185 [0.000] (0.052)	-0.259 [0.000] (0.074)	-0.184 [0.000] (0.051)	-0.258 [0.001] (0.074)	-0.183 [0.000] (0.051)
Same Country	2.850 [0.000] (0.352)	2.792 [0.000] (0.213)	2.847 [0.000] (0.352)	2.804 [0.000] (0.213)	2.846 [0.000] (0.353)	2.811 [0.000] (0.212)
Company Country FE		Yes		Yes		Yes
Industry (NACE) FE		Yes		Yes		Yes
Time Period FE		Yes		Yes		Yes
Number of Investor X Company Dyads		12,526		12,526		12,526
Log Likelihood		-1,622.509		-1,619.455		-1,614.938

Brackets: p-values; parentheses: standard errors clustered by investor.

Table 5 - Marginal effects of radical invention on the type of investment tie

	Model 2	Model 3	
		(I)	(II)
<i>Marginal effect of Radical Invention on:</i>			
P(Dealtype = Unrealized Tie)	-0.009 [0.054] (0.005)	-0.004 [0.421] (0.005)	-0.024 [0.013] (0.010)
P(Dealtype = Standalone Tie)	-0.000 [0.895] (0.002)	0.001 [0.760] (0.003)	-0.004 [0.277] (0.004)
P(Dealtype = Syndicated Tie)	0.010 [0.034] (0.005)	0.003 [0.474] (0.005)	0.028 [0.004] (0.010)
<i>Variables included:</i>			
Radical Invention	YES	YES	
Reputable Investor	YES	YES	
Radical Invention X Reputable Investor	NO	YES	
All other independent variables	YES	YES	
<i>Variables specified:</i>			
Reputable Investor = 1	-	NO	YES
Hypothesis	H1	H2	
Number of Investor X Company Dyads	12,526	12,526	

Brackets: p-values; parentheses: standard errors clustered by investor. Model 2 reports the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* on the three outcomes associated to *Dealtype*. Model 3-I reports the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* when *Reputable Investor* = 0. Model 3-II reports the corresponding marginal effects when *Reputable Investor* = 1.

APPENDIX

Table A1 - Marginal effects of radical invention (global scale) on the type of investment tie

	Model 4	Model 5	
		(I)	(II)
<i>Marginal effect of Radical Invention (global scale) on:</i>			
P(Dealtype = Unrealized Tie)	-0.007 [0.093] (0.004)	-0.002 [0.738] (0.005)	-0.025 [0.010] (0.010)
P(Dealtype = Standalone Tie)	-0.001 [0.690] (0.002)	0.000 [0.902] (0.002)	-0.004 [0.230] (0.003)
P(Dealtype = Syndicated Tie)	0.008 [0.047] (0.004)	0.001 [0.759] (0.004)	0.028 [0.002] (0.009)
<i>Variables included:</i>			
Radical Invention (global)	YES		YES
Reputable Investor	YES		YES
Radical Invention (global) X Reputable Investor	NO		YES
All other independent variables	YES		YES
<i>Variables specified:</i>			
Reputable Investor = 1	-	NO	YES
Number of Investor X Company Dyads	12,526		12,526

Brackets: p-values; parentheses: standard errors clustered by investor. Model 4 reports the marginal effects of *Radical Invention (global scale)* on the three outcomes associated to *Dealtype*. Model 5-I reports the marginal effects of *Radical Invention (global scale)* when *Reputable Investor* = 0. Model 5-II reports the corresponding marginal effects when *Reputable Investor* = 1.

Table A2 - Marginal effects of radical invention on the type of investment tie for different variable specifications of investor reputation

	Model 6				Model 7		Model 8	
	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(I)	(II)	(I)	(II)
<i>Marginal effect of Radical Invention on:</i>								
P(Dealtype = Unrealized Tie)	-0.008 [0.116] (0.005)	-0.009 [0.063] (0.005)	-0.011 [0.037] (0.005)	-0.013 [0.032] (0.006)	-0.005 [0.320] (0.005)	-0.022 [0.021] (0.009)	-0.007 [0.245] (0.006)	-0.016 [0.067] (0.009)
P(Dealtype = Standalone Tie)	0.001 [0.699] (0.003)	-0.001 [0.719] (0.002)	-0.003 [0.273] (0.003)	-0.005 [0.168] (0.003)	0.000 [0.929] (0.003)	-0.002 [0.595] (0.004)	0.001 [0.603] (0.003)	-0.005 [0.178] (0.004)
P(Dealtype = Syndicated Tie)	0.007 [0.123] (0.005)	0.010 [0.036] (0.005)	0.014 [0.008] (0.005)	0.017 [0.006] (0.006)	0.005 [0.301] (0.005)	0.024 [0.009] (0.009)	0.005 [0.317] (0.005)	0.021 [0.015] (0.009)
<i>Variables included:</i>								
Radical Invention		YES			YES		YES	
Investor Reputation (continuous)		YES			NO		NO	
Reputable Investor (#IPO 3 years)		NO			YES		NO	
Reputable Investor (#investments 5 years)		NO			NO		YES	
Radical Invention X Investor Reputation (continuous)		YES			NO		NO	
Radical Invention X Reputable Investor (#IPO 3 years)		NO			YES		NO	
Radical Invention X Reputable Investor (#investments 5 years)		NO			NO		YES	
All other independent variables		YES			YES		YES	
<i>Variables specified:</i>								
Investor Reputation (continuous)	p50	p75	p90	p95	-	-	-	-
Reputable Investor (#IPO 3 years) = 1	-	-	-	-	NO	YES	-	-
Reputable Investor (#investments 5 years) = 1	-	-	-	-	-	-	NO	YES
Number of Investor X Company Dyads	12,526				12,526		12,526	

Brackets: p-values; parentheses: standard errors clustered by investor. Model 6 reports the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* at different values of underlying distribution of investor reputation: median (I), the 75th (II), the 90th (III), and the 95th (IV) percentile. Model 7 reports the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* when *Reputable Investor (#IPO 3 years)* = 0 (Model 7-I) and when it equals 1 (Model 7-II). Model 8 reports the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* when *Reputable Investor (#investments 5 years)* = 0 (Model 8-I) and when it equals 1 (Model 8-II).

Table A3 - Marginal effects of radical invention on the type of investment tie for different model specifications

	Model 9	Model 10		Model 11	Model 12	
		(I)	(II)		(I)	(II)
<i>Marginal effect of Radical Invention on:</i>						
P(Dealtype = Unrealized Tie)	-0.009 [0.024] (0.004)	-0.004 [0.357] (0.005)	-0.024 [0.020] (0.011)	-0.036 [0.055] (0.019)	-0.022 [0.320] (0.022)	-0.066 [0.023] (0.029)
P(Dealtype = Standalone Tie)	-0.000 [0.891] (0.002)	0.001 [0.754] (0.003)	-0.004 [0.273] (0.004)	-0.002 [0.859] (0.009)	0.004 [0.740] (0.011)	-0.015 [0.188] (0.011)
P(Dealtype = Syndicated Tie)	0.010 [0.039] (0.005)	0.003 [0.479] (0.005)	0.028 [0.007] (0.011)	0.037 [0.036] (0.018)	0.018 [0.370] (0.020)	0.081 [0.007] (0.030)
<i>Variables included:</i>						
Radical Invention	YES	YES		YES	YES	
Reputable Investor	YES	YES		YES	YES	
Radical Invention X Reputable Investor	NO	YES		NO	YES	
All other independent variables	YES	YES		YES	YES	
<i>Variables specified:</i>						
Reputable Investor = 1	-	NO	YES	-	NO	YES
<i>Model specifications:</i>						
Matching by Year X Country	NO	NO		YES	YES	
SE Clustered by Company	YES	YES		NO	NO	
SE Clustered by Investor	NO	NO		YES	YES	
Number of Investor X Company Dyads	12,526	12,526		3,172	3,172	

Brackets: p-values; parentheses: standard errors. Model 9 and 10 report the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* when clustering standard errors at the level of the company. Model 11 and 12 report the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* when applying a matching at the level of the year and country.

Table A4 – Descriptive statistics of 1000 simulations with random draws of counterfactuals by company without replacement

	Resampling			Model 2				Model 3							
	Repetitions	Unrealized Ties	Realized Ties	mean	sd	mean p-value	# p-value >= 0.1	mean	Sd	(I) mean p-value	# p-value >= 0.1	mean	sd	(II) mean p-value	# p-value >= 0.1
<i>Marginal effect of Radical Invention on:</i>															
P(Dealtype = Unrealized Tie)	1,000	3,080	433	-0.024	0.005	0.122	513	-0.013	0.006	0.422	987	-0.054	0.012	0.082	285
	1,000	1,540	433	-0.035	0.010	0.157	612	-0.022	0.011	0.420	963	-0.072	0.022	0.141	507
P(Dealtype = Standalone Tie)	1,000	3,080	433	-0.001	0.001	0.840	1,000	0.004	0.002	0.704	1,000	-0.017	0.002	0.186	928
	1,000	1,540	433	-0.003	0.002	0.784	1,000	0.006	0.003	0.702	1,000	-0.033	0.004	0.129	657
P(Dealtype = Syndicated Tie)	1,000	3,080	433	0.025	0.004	0.083	276	0.010	0.004	0.519	1,000	0.071	0.011	0.021	7
	1,000	1,540	433	0.038	0.008	0.105	427	0.016	0.009	0.536	999	0.105	0.019	0.031	49
<i>Variables included:</i>															
Radical Invention						YES								YES	
Reputable Investor						YES								YES	
Radical Invention X Reputable Investor						NO								YES	
All other independent variables						YES								YES	
<i>Variables specified:</i>															
Reputable Investor = 1						-				NO				YES	

Descriptive results from 1,000 simulations of Model 2 and Model 3, where we take into account 10 or 5 unrealized ties for each realized ties. For each of the 1,000 repetitions, we randomly draw 5 or 10 unrealized ties without replacement. We dropped investment ties in year 2015, because only 3 companies have been financed by three distinct independent VCs in that year. Hence, we cannot build a counterfactual of 5 or 10 unrealized ties to other distinct investors, which have been active in that year. We therefore observe 433 realized investment ties between 2003 and 2014 for 308 companies. When the random assignment is 1 to 5 (10), the number of unrealized ties is 1,540 (3,080). We report mean values and standard deviations of the marginal effects of *Radical Invention* on the probabilities of our different categories of *Dealtype*. In addition, we report the average p-values and the frequencies of p-values that are equal or larger than 10 percent.

Table A5 – *Testing the assumption of the independence of irrelevant alternatives*

Outcome reference: Unrealized Tie vs.	Model 13		Model 14	Model 15
	Standalone Tie	Syndicated Tie	Standalone Tie	Syndicated Tie
Radical Invention	-0.278 [0.298] (0.267)	0.389 [0.003] (0.130)	-0.278 [0.298] (0.267)	0.389 [0.003] (0.130)
Reputable Investor	-0.030 [0.891] (0.217)	-0.024 [0.740] (0.073)	-0.031 [0.887] (0.217)	-0.024 [0.737] (0.073)
Number of Investor X Company Dyads	12,526		12,193	12,423
Log Likelihood	-2,125.871		-593.742	-1,529.388

Brackets: p-values; parentheses: standard errors clustered by investor. The coefficients represent the changes in the log-odds. Model 13 represents a full multinomial logit model with all three outcome categories. In Model 14 and 15, we restrict our sample to unrealized and standalone ties (Model 14) and unrealized and syndicated ties (Model 15) and estimated the coefficients with a logistic regression.

Table A6 – Results of the multinomial and logistic regressions conditioned either on the company or the investor

Outcome reference: Unrealized Tie vs.	Model 16		Model 17	Model 18
	Standalone Tie	Syndicated Tie	Standalone Tie	Syndicated Tie
Radical Invention			-0.185 [0.653] (0.413)	0.156 [0.406] (0.187)
Reputable Investor	0.087 [0.809] (0.357)	-0.199 [0.355] (0.215)	0.256 [0.782] (0.927)	-0.604 [0.216] (0.488)
Radical Invention X Reputable Investor	-0.244 [0.781] (0.877)	0.578 [0.093] (0.344)	-0.589 [0.495] (0.863)	0.938 [0.003] (0.321)
Forward Citations (log)			-0.154 [0.173] (0.113)	0.131 [0.011] (0.051)
Average Patent Family Size			0.005 [0.776] (0.019)	0.017 [0.088] (0.01)
Company Age			0.016 [0.744] (0.05)	-0.008 [0.768] (0.027)
Industry Experience (log)	0.009 [0.940] (0.114)	0.095 [0.129] (0.062)	-0.026 [0.926] (0.281)	0.079 [0.680] (0.192)
Distance (log)	-0.372 [0.000] (0.098)	-0.194 [0.000] (0.050)	-0.478 [0.000] (0.098)	-0.332 [0.000] (0.048)
Same Country	2.682 [0.000] (0.374)	2.747 [0.000] (0.208)	3.695 [0.000] (0.566)	3.353 [0.000] (0.254)
Company Country FE		NO	YES	YES
Industry (NACE) FE		NO	YES	YES
Time Period FE		NO	YES	YES
Conditioned on Company		YES	NO	NO
Conditioned on Investor		NO	YES	YES
Number of Investor X Company Dyads		10,868	4,624	10,803
Log Likelihood		-961.39	-236.139	-783.213

Brackets: p-values; parentheses: standard errors. The coefficients represent the changes in the log-odds. Model 16 represents a full multinomial logit model with all three outcome categories that that is conditioned on company. Model 17 and 18 represent simple conditional logit analyses and are conditioned on investor. They separately compare standalone ties to unrealized ties (Model 17) and syndicated ties to unrealized ties (Model 18).

Table A7 - Frequency table of companies with at least one radical invention by their location in a VC hub

	VC Hub = 0		VC Hub = 1	
Panel A: VC Hubs London, Paris				
<i>All companies with</i>	N	%	N	%
Radical Invention = 0	260	80.75	34	85.00
Radical Invention = 1	62	19.25	6	15.00
Total	322	100.00	40	100.00
Panel B: VC Hubs London, Paris, Stockholm, Munich, Helsinki				
<i>All companies with</i>	N	%	N	%
Radical Invention = 0	252	81.55	42	79.25
Radical Invention = 1	57	18.45	11	20.75
Total	309	100.00	53	100.00
Panel C: VC Hubs London, Paris, Stockholm, Munich, Helsinki, Amsterdam, Berlin, Dublin, Copenhagen, Bonn				
<i>All companies with</i>	N	%	N	%
Radical Invention = 0	228	80.85	66	82.50
Radical Invention = 1	54	19.15	14	17.50
Total	282	100.00	80	100.00